

AGE ASPECTS OF CLINICAL MANIFESTATIONS OF IRRITABLE BOWEL SYNDROME IN CHILDREN

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Abstract. *The article analyzes the irritable bowel syndrome in children, depending on age, sex and clinical options. More pronounced clinical symptoms observed in children's intestine functional disorders in comparison with clinical diseases of the upper gastrointestinal tract without irritable bowel syndrome. Predominant irritable bowel syndrome is diarrhea, constipation, pain and bloating that occurs more frequently in older children (12-14 years), particularly among boys. Thus, in our studies, all major clinical scores prevalent in boys.*

Keywords: *functional bowel disorder, irritable bowel syndrome, dyspepsia, school age, flatulence.*

Аннотация. *В статье анализируется синдром раздраженного кишечника у детей в зависимости от возраста, пола и клинического варианта. Более выраженные клинические симптомы отмечаются у детей с функциональными расстройствами кишечника по сравнению с клиникой заболеваний верхних отделов пищеварительного тракта без синдрома раздраженного кишечника. Преобладающим синдромом раздраженного кишечника является диарея с запорами, болями и метеоризмом, что встречается чаще у детей старшего возраста (12-14 лет), в частности у мальчиков. Таким образом, по результатам наших исследований, все основные клинические показатели преобладают у мальчиков.*

Ключевые слова: *функциональные расстройства кишечника, синдром раздраженного кишечника, диспепсия, школьный возраст, метеоризм.*

In the last decade, there has been not only a lack of a trend towards a decrease in the prevalence of pathology of the digestive tract in children, but its steady increase. It is emphasized that in 90% of cases, abdominal pain in children is caused by functional disorders and only in 10% by organic disorders [1]. Functional disorders can be considered various combinations of gastrointestinal symptoms without structural or biochemical abnormalities [4]. It is necessary to note the increasing share and practical significance of functional diseases of the digestive system in pediatric gastroenterology. One of the main factors in the formation of this pathology is acute and chronic stress, the role of which in the life of a person, including a child, is constantly increasing [2; 3].

Purpose of the study. to study the clinical picture of the course of irritable bowel syndrome in children depending on the clinical variant of the disease, age, and gender.

Materials and methods. The main group (group 1) consisted of 56 children suffering from irritable bowel syndrome, aged 7-14 years (average age 10.0 ± 0.69 years), of which 30 were girls and 26 boys. The comparison group (group 2) consisted of 100 patients with diseases of the upper digestive tract without IBS. The diagnosis of irritable bowel syndrome was established based on the criteria for IBS defined by the III Rome Consensus. All children underwent the following examinations: clinical examination, a generally accepted set of studies for patients with gastrointestinal pathology.

Results and discussion. In our study, young children accounted for $42.2 \pm 4.6\%$, older children - $57.8 \pm 4.6\%$. It was found that in the younger age group the disease is more often detected

in boys - $57.4 \pm 7.2\%$, and in girls this figure was $42.6 \pm 7.2\%$ ($p < 0.05$), in the older age group in for girls - $68.1 \pm 5.6\%$, and for boys - $31.9 \pm 5.4\%$ ($p < 0.05$). The factor contributing to the development of the disease in most children was the presence of allergic diseases - $28.4 \pm 4.2\%$, and in the comparison group - $10 \pm 3.0\%$ ($p < 0.01$), with food allergies playing the largest role - $3.8\% \pm 1.1$, in the comparison group this figure was $7.0 \pm 2.6\%$. A history of intestinal infections was present in $20.7 \pm 3.6\%$ ($p < 0.01$) of children, and in the comparison group - in $18.9 \pm 2.9\%$ ($p < 0.05$), more often the presence of previous yersiniosis was noted, identified in $5.2 \pm 2.1\%$ of patients, and in the comparison group - in $1.0 \pm 0.9\%$ ($p > 0.05$). An important factor was obesity, detected in $18.8 \pm 3.6\%$ of children in the main group and in $9.0 \pm 2.9\%$ of patients in the comparison group ($p < 0.01$). It was found that about a third of patients ($31 \pm 4.3\%$) with IBS are brought up in single-parent families (without a father or without a mother), which has a negative impact on the psychological status of patients and is a factor in the development of the disease. When analyzing the clinical course of the disease, it was found that the main symptom of the disease was pain with high frequency. The connection between pain and defecation was noted in $89.8 \pm 4.3\%$ of young children. Of these, there were $53 \pm 4.1\%$ boys, and $36 \pm 3.5\%$ girls. In older children, this figure was $92.5 \pm 3.2\%$ ($p > 0.05$). Of these, for boys it was $49.2 \pm 4.8\%$, and for girls - $43 \pm 3.2\%$. The connection between pain and changes in stool frequency according to the type of diarrhea was noted in $30.6 \pm 6.6\%$ of the main group of children, of which in boys this figure was $18 \pm 2.9\%$, and in girls - $12.1 \pm 1.1\%$. In the comparison group, the rate was $31.3 \pm 5.7\%$ ($p > 0.05$). The connection between pain and impaired stool frequency, such as constipation, was found in $42.9 \pm 7.1\%$ of older children; in the comparison group it was $26.9 \pm 5.4\%$ ($p > 0.05$) at the same age. Peculiarities of pain syndrome in patients associated with the act of defecation were identified ($91.4 \pm 2.6\%$). Episodes of psycho-emotional stress were detected in $26.7 \pm 4.1\%$ of patients; $24.1 \pm 4.0\%$ of children had spastic pain. An interesting fact was that pain syndrome in 99% of cases occurred precisely in those children who did poorly at school. It is characteristic that in $40.5 \pm 4.6\%$ of the examined older girls the pain was localized in the lower abdomen. The characteristics of the pain syndrome can also include a history of hospitalization in patients with IBS with "suspicion of acute appendicitis" - $17.2 \pm 3.5\%$ of patients (in the comparison group - $10.0 \pm 3.0\%$ of children, $p > 0.05$). The feeling of incomplete emptying after defecation in the main group with diarrhea was detected in $50.0 \pm 8.8\%$. Of these, $37.5 \pm 5.1\%$ were boys and $22.5 \pm 3.4\%$ were girls. Constipation was observed in $17.9 \pm 6.1\%$ of children ($p < 0.01$). Of these, $10.5 \pm 2.1\%$ were boys, $8.4 \pm 1.4\%$ were girls. Flatulence was detected in $75.0 \pm 7.6\%$ of patients with diarrhea ($p < 0.01$). In $98.2 \pm 7.3\%$ of children with IBS, pain and flatulence were combined in almost all children ($p < 0.05$). Of these, $38.5 \pm 4.8\%$ were young children, and $60.7 \pm 7.8\%$ were older children. Urgency with diarrhea was also slightly more common ($21.9 \pm 7.3\%$) in older boys with IBS compared with pain and flatulence ($19.5 \pm 6.2\%$ of patients, $p > 0.05$).

Thus, according to the results of our research, all main clinical indicators predominate in boys, both younger and older.

Conclusions

1. More pronounced clinical symptoms are observed in children with functional intestinal disorders compared to clinical diseases of the upper digestive tract without irritable bowel syndrome.
2. The predominant irritable bowel syndrome is diarrhea with constipation, pain and flatulence, which is more common in older children (12-14 years old), particularly boys.

LITERATURE

1. Akopyan A.I., Belmer S.V., Karpina L.M. Calprotectin in stool in functional disorders of the digestive organs as a marker of minimal inflammation // Materials of the XIX Congress of Pediatric Gastroenterologists of Russia and the CIS Countries. Moscow, 2012. pp. 28-29.
2. Belmer S.V., Kovalenko A.A., Akopyan A.N. Irritable bowel syndrome: new horizons of drug therapy // Attending physician, 2012. No. 2. P. 68-72.
3. Drossman D. A. Presidential Address: Gastrointestinal illness and Biopsychosocial Model. //PsychosomMed., 1998. 60. P. 258-267.
4. Richardson G., Griffiths A.M., Miller V., Thomas A.G. Quality of life in inflammatory bowel disease // A crosscultural comparison of English and Canadian children // Journal of Pediatric Gastroenterology and Nutrition, 2001. P. 32- 578.
5. Camilleri M, Park SY, Scarpato E, Staiano A. Exploring hypotheses and rationale for causes of infantile colic. Neurogastroenterol Motil 2017; 29 (2).
6. Liu X, Silverman A, Kern M. Excessive coupling of the salience network with intrinsic neurocognitive brain networks during rectal distension in adolescents with irritable bowel syndrome: a preliminary report. Neuro gastroenterol Motil 2016; 28 (1): 43–53.
7. Hubbard CS, Becerra L, Heinz N et al. Abdominal pain, the adolescent and altered brain structure and function. PLoS One 2016; 11 (5): e0156545. 17.
8. Drossman D.A. Functional Gastrointestinal Disorders: History, Pathophysiology, Clinical Features, and Rome IV. Gastroenterology 2016; 150 (6): 1262–79.
9. Zakharova I.N., Sugyan N.G., Berezhnaya I.V. Functional gastrointestinal disorders in young children: diagnostic criteria and approaches to diet therapy. Ross. Vestn. perinatology and pediatrics. 2018; 63 (1): 113–21.
10. Kiyomova Sh. O., Koshimbetova G. K. Modern view on the problem of irritable bowel syndrome //International scientific research 2018. pp. 286-288.
11. Koshimbetova G.K. et al. Clinical manifestations of irritable bowel syndrome in children //The Seventh International Conference on Eurasian scientific development. – 2015.-P.61-64.
12. Koshimbetova G.K., Shomansurova E.A. Aspects of functional diseases of the gastrointestinal tract in children // Scientific search in the modern world. – 2017. – pp. 84-85.